

HARMONISED PRACTICES, REGULATIONS AND STANDARDS
IN WASTE MANAGEMENT AND DECOMMISSIONING

Deliverable D3.2

WP3 Cross Border Waste Management Summary Position Paper

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Executive Summary

Work Package (WP) 3 of HARPERS has explored the most important needs and challenges associated with wider implementation of cross-border services and/or facilities for radioactive waste management activities across Europe. As these needs and challenges have been identified, we are now able to define ways in which to address or overcome them, resulting in a series of recommendations and actions that will provide solutions for obstacles to common standards for implementation of cross-border services, circular economy practices and advanced technologies, which strengthens the Member States (MS) common market for public and private initiatives.

WP3 objective:

This work package aims to identify the most important needs and opportunities for current and future cross border radioactive waste management activities (i.e., characterisation, treatment, conditioning, and storage) and assess regulatory obstacles to providing such services (with WP6). The outcomes will provide MS, the EC and other interested stakeholders with guidance on advancing safe and efficient cross border service/facility possibilities in radioactive waste management.

HARPERS WP3 identified key priority areas critical for Cross Border Waste Management and the project analysed existing regulatory discrepancies (Please refer to the List of selection criteria for prioritization of topics [8]), case studies from various countries (Defined in detail in the memorandums for tasks 3.2a, b, c – please refer to reference [3,4,5]) and developed a series of “Cases for Change” based on this evidence that are focused on improving Waste Management across the Member States (MS) (As defined in the WP3 business case [2]). This Position Paper provides a summary of the main findings from WorkPackage 3 –Cross Border Services/Facilities for radioactive waste management activities across Europe. It outlines advancements within the waste management activities from an intra and inter MS perspective, and highlights the potential benefits, challenges, and recommendations for implementation across Europe.

Section 1 discusses the Nuclear Industry Challenges and how they can impact the implementation of cross border nuclear waste management as well as the benefits that could be brought.

Section 2 summarises the collected experiences in cross border waste management as well as examples of successful cross border treatments.

Section 3 discusses the Challenges and Opportunities for the further development and engagement of cross border waste management, based on the benefits that it can bring.

Section 0 summarises the main Conclusions and the proposed Recommendations for approaching harmonisation to facilitate the transition towards a cross-border waste management.

By addressing regulatory challenges and fostering collaboration among stakeholders, the nuclear industry can transition towards more waste treatment drawing on MS experience and aligned with the waste hierarchy to ensure that legacy, current and future wastes are treated economically and effectively.

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FIGURE

Figure 1 - Waste Hierarchy

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1 Introduction

It is well recognized that Radioactive Waste Management should follow the principles of the waste hierarchy (Figure 1.). This in turn, supports the application of Cross Border Waste Management to bring benefits to nuclear decommissioning and radioactive waste management, such as minimizing waste, increasing efficiency (lower costs, and reduced risk of delays), and enhancing sustainability. Nevertheless, there are challenges ahead in implementing cross border radioactive waste management across Europe.

Figure 1 The waste management hierarchy.

As one of the technical work packages of the HARPERS project, through a first identification of the main priority areas and a subsequent analysis of the existing challenges and well-established experiences, HARPERS WP3 addressed the conditions and opportunities for promoting Cross Border Waste Management approaches when managing materials and waste arising from nuclear decommissioning across Europe.

1.1 Nuclear Industry and challenges

The generation of nuclear energy has long played a pivotal role in supporting the energy needs of European Union (EU) Member States. With its potential to provide a stable and low-carbon energy supply, nuclear power contributes significantly to the EU's broader energy transition and climate goals. However, alongside its advantages, nuclear energy production inevitably results in the creation of radioactive waste. This challenge that demands careful and coordinated management to ensure both environmental safety and public health.

As in almost all historic industrial endeavours, waste related matters were not always solved before starting to implement new technologies. Nuclear energy and research also suffer from similar historic challenges, needing solutions. Furthermore, many small quantities of challenging waste forms not suitable to dispose of as is, makes the challenge to solve them nationally even more suitable for international cooperation and solutions.

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Nuclear waste management encompasses all activities associated with handling, treating, storing, and disposing of radioactive materials generated at various stages of the nuclear fuel cycle. These materials range from low-level waste, such as contaminated tools and clothing, to high-level waste, primarily spent nuclear fuel. Each category presents unique technical, logistical, and societal challenges, necessitating tailored solutions.

In the European context, the diversity among MS in terms of nuclear power reliance and waste management infrastructure underscores the importance of a unified yet flexible approach. While countries such as Finland, France and Sweden have advanced systems for nuclear waste storage and disposal, others rely on shared expertise and collaborative frameworks. The EU's policy on nuclear waste management is guided by the 2011 Radioactive Waste and Spent Fuel Management Directive, which establishes a legal framework for safe and sustainable waste handling across all MS. This directive emphasizes national responsibility, transparency, and long-term solutions such as geological disposal.

Cross-border waste treatment has emerged as a critical component of the EU's nuclear waste management strategy. In cases where MS lack the necessary facilities for processing or storing certain types of radioactive waste, they may collaborate with neighbouring countries that possess more advanced infrastructure. This practice not only optimizes the use of existing resources but also fosters solidarity and shared responsibility within the EU. However, such arrangements require rigorous regulatory oversight and clear agreements to ensure safety, equity, and adherence to international standards.

Public engagement and trust are crucial elements of nuclear waste management strategies. Across Europe, governments and nuclear operators work to involve local communities in decision-making processes, particularly regarding the siting of long-term storage facilities. Robust scientific research, coupled with transparent communication, helps build confidence in the safety and reliability of these measures.

As Europe advances its clean energy ambitions, the sustainable and secure management of nuclear waste will remain a cornerstone of nuclear energy policy. By fostering international collaboration, investing in innovative technologies, and prioritizing environmental stewardship, European MS aim to set a global standard for responsible nuclear waste management.

1.2 Challenges of Cross-Border Nuclear Waste Treatment in European Member States

The treatment and management of nuclear waste across borders present a complex set of challenges for EU Member States. While cross-border collaboration offers opportunities for optimizing resources and leveraging advanced infrastructure, it also raises technical, legal, and social concerns. Addressing these challenges is essential to ensure the safety, sustainability, and efficiency of nuclear waste management within the EU.

1. Regulatory Disparities

One of the primary challenges in cross-border nuclear waste treatment is the disparity in national regulatory frameworks. While the EU's 2011 Radioactive Waste and Spent Fuel

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Management Directive provides overarching guidelines, each member state implements its own policies and standards for handling, processing, and storing radioactive materials. Differences in licensing procedures, safety requirements, terminology, and waste classification can complicate cross-border agreements and lead to delays in waste transfer and treatment.

2. Transportation Risks

The movement of radioactive waste across national borders involves significant logistical and safety risks. Transporting nuclear materials requires specialized containers, secure routes, and strict adherence to international safety standards. Potential risks include accidents, environmental contamination, and security threats such as theft or sabotage. These risks necessitate rigorous planning, coordination, and real-time monitoring, which can be resource-intensive and technically demanding. It can also involve transition through countries with no nuclear related activities, which can be politically more sensitive as well as regulatory competence challenging.

3. Public Opposition and Perception

Public resistance to cross-border nuclear waste treatment is a significant obstacle. Communities often express concerns about the potential health and environmental impacts of transporting and processing radioactive materials near their homes. Public perception of nuclear waste as a high-risk and long-lasting hazard amplifies these concerns. Governments and operators face challenges in fostering trust and ensuring transparency, particularly in regions with limited prior exposure to nuclear activities.

4. Equity and Responsibility

Questions of equity and responsibility arise when nuclear waste is treated or stored in countries other than where it was generated. Some MS may perceive cross-border arrangements as unfair, particularly if they involve long-term storage facilities located within their borders. This can lead to political tensions and disagreements over the equitable distribution of risks, benefits, and financial responsibilities associated with nuclear waste management.

5. Technical and Infrastructure Limitations

Not all EU member states have the technical expertise or infrastructure required for advanced nuclear waste treatment. Cross-border cooperation often depends on the availability of specialized facilities in countries like France, Sweden, or Finland. However, these facilities have limited capacities and may prioritize their domestic waste, leading to potential bottlenecks and delays in addressing the needs of other member states.

6. Compliance with International Agreements

Cross-border nuclear waste treatment must comply with a range of international agreements, including those established by the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA). Ensuring that all parties adhere to these agreements can be challenging, particularly in cases where national

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interests conflict with international obligations. Misalignments in compliance can result in legal disputes and undermine trust between member states.

7. Financial Considerations

The cost of cross-border nuclear waste treatment is another significant challenge. Transportation, processing, and long-term storage require substantial financial investment. Disagreements over cost-sharing arrangements can hinder progress on cross-border initiatives. Additionally, ensuring that funds are allocated transparently and equitably remains a critical issue for fostering trust and cooperation.

1.3 Potential Benefits of Cross Border Waste Management

As Europe continues to develop and gain confidence in waste management, we can see through current cross border projects such as metal recycling, incineration and also high level waste transformation (making exotic uranium-compounds into stable uranium oxide), that there are benefits to waste owners (technical and economic) as well as to the environment and giving confidence to the public that the industry is aligned to the waste hierarchy and will deal with the waste arising from legacy and decommissioning projects.

The collective understanding and experience within Europe present a significant opportunity to further the advancement of waste treatment for both simple (e.g. metal recycling) and complex waste forms (e.g. problematic waste such as resin). As technology and experience advance, academia, regulators, industry and other stakeholders are working towards the next developments, processes, solutions for a variety of wastes forms. This movement will allow waste owners the opportunity to align with the waste hierarchy for their waste forms and to actually treat and reuse/dispose of waste instead of temporarily storing it. There are a number of challenges relating to volumes of inventory (e.g. an MS might only have a small inventory) and regulatory aspects which need to be over come and this is where MS can benefit from cross border waste management.

As the new build market for large scale and smaller scale reactors (SMR's and AMR's) gathers pace confidence in waste arisings and management needs to demonstrate to governments, the public, regulators and other stakeholders. Waste will be a large hinder in case there are no waste routes for some waste these new coming reactor types bring¹. Cross border waste management can support this growing sector and will help to provide the confidence needed to ensure successful delivery and operation.

1.4 HARPERS WP3 Context

In the first phase HARPERS WP3 was dedicated to the identification (through stakeholder interaction) of the priority areas for Cross Border Waste Management considerations **Error!**

¹ New potential waste forms were not part of the HARPERS project. However, it should be noted that establishing waste routes for the new solutions proposed will be a key to establish these on the market, and international cooperation can be one of several keys to do so.

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Reference source not found.. Task 3.1 is focused on the prioritisation of needs and opportunities for cross-border service/facility considerations, including a gap analysis exercise and they were proposed for deeper analysis later in the project. The final list was then grouped in 3 main topics covering Best Practice/Harmonisation, Technical Challenges, and Geological Disposal Facility (GDF).

Following further rounds of engagement, the different challenges, needs, issues, recommendations are reported together with their origin and 3 topics were identified to be further developed:

CATEGORY	TOPIC n.	WHAT (Challenge/Need)
Harmonisation	1	Harmonisation of Individual EU and international countries problematic waste inventory
	4	To align wastes with treatment technologies in a manner acceptable to all stakeholders
Best Practice	7	Member States approach to dealing with radioactive contaminated hazardous waste differs

This position paper provides the outcome of the process undertaken for this WP, based on a process of topic identification, prioritization, gap analysis, topic development and justification through TECOP (Technical, Economical, Commercial, Organizational, Political-Societal) risk analysis framework. These activities gave rise to suggest regulatory impacts and cases for change to take forwards. The results of the project from the initial project phases based on the original needs and challenges, through the refinement processes and topic selection, which has provided us with the above three topics that will help to realize some of the benefits outlines above spanning scientific/technical, economic, societal, environmental, and regulatory impacts.

The documentation that has supported this position paper and which provides further details of the path that WP3 has taken include:

- Milestone 3.5: Regulatory Framework and Criteria Report [1]
- Milestone 3.6: Business Case Report [2]
- Task 3.2a Memo [3]
- Task 3.2b Memo [4]
- Task 3.2c Memo [5]

Earlier documentation includes:

- Deliverable 3.1: Prioritisation of identified topics [6]
- Milestone 3.1: List of thematic questions to Phase 1 [7]
- Milestone 3.2: List of selection criteria for prioritization of topics in Phase 1 [8]
- Milestone 3.3: Update to revised DoA (WP3) [9]

2 Applications (current state)

The current cross-border radioactive waste management activities include:

1. Shared Use of Advanced Treatment Facilities

Several EU Member States without domestic capabilities for handling certain types of radioactive waste rely on neighboring countries with advanced treatment facilities. For example, countries such as Belgium and the Netherlands send specific categories of radioactive waste to France for processing, leveraging France's nuclear infrastructure. Several countries send metal and incinerable waste to Sweden for treatment. This has been supported by the Swedish society for decades for the treatment of others waste at Swedish waste treatment facilities, assisted by the mandatory return of the radioactive residues.

2. Collaborative Research and Development Projects

Cross-border collaboration extends to joint research initiatives aimed at improving radioactive waste treatment technologies. Programs such as the EU's Horizon Europe fund research into safer and more efficient methods for processing and storing nuclear waste, with participation from multiple member states and international partners.

3. Transport and Interim Storage Agreements

Agreements between member states facilitate the transport of radioactive materials for interim storage. There are also established waste routes between countries based on collaborations in waste treatment which have lasted for more than 10 years. These have been developed under existing regulations and have been taking the differences into account.

The conclusion is that these actions are possible, however, there is limited MS harmonization in place.

5. Regulatory and Technical Cooperation

EU member states work closely together through organizations such as the European Nuclear Safety Regulators Group (ENSREG) to harmonize safety standards and share best practices in radioactive waste management. This cooperation ensures consistency and compliance with international safety and environmental guidelines. MS set different priorities for managing nuclear waste based on political, environmental, or public concerns, however sometimes there is a lack of policy or infrastructure. Some countries may not have clear policies or sufficient infrastructure to handle waste, leading to delays or inaction.

6. Economic Considerations

Treating nuclear waste can be expensive and some countries lack the financial resources or economic justification to invest in such technologies. In addition, countries with smaller nuclear industries/inventories may not see the need to develop costly infrastructure for waste treatment if the volume of waste is relatively low.

7. Technological Capability

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Some nuclear waste treatment methods, require specialized technology and expertise that some countries may not possess. Also some countries rely on others to manage their waste, exporting it to nations with better-developed infrastructure.

8. Volume and Type of Nuclear Waste

Countries with extensive nuclear energy programmes, treat nuclear waste extensively because they generate large amounts. Countries with smaller nuclear industries may store waste temporarily without treatment. It should also be noted that there are differences in terminology and meanings for waste types across MS and this can also lead to inefficiency and introduce difficulties or obstacles to efficient waste treatment options.

Whilst this is a start, more can be done to realize the benefits as stated above and these have been captured in the Regulatory Impact and the Business Case Milestones for WP3, which are summarized below.

The summary provided above presents an overview of the information, opinions and activities that have been uncovered in this WP. However, there are clear and positive examples that cross border waste treatment facilities provides a significant benefit to MS and that additional cases for change and supportive regulatory impacts can be made to further improve waste management in Europe.

3 Challenges and opportunities

MS need to identify and utilise a suitable waste management strategy which takes into account all of the considerations and factors identified above, and this presents both challenges and opportunities. This section explores the potential benefits and impacts of treating nuclear waste across borders and helps to address both the technical and regulatory aspects.

3.1 Summary of findings for the Harmonisation of Individual EU and international countries problematic waste inventory

The main conclusions drawn from the assessment of obtained information during this task are summarised below.

3.1.1 Level of Cross-border Cooperation and Partnerships in RAW Challenges

The majority of European countries consider the NPPs as the primary source of radioactive waste in their country and have collaborations or partnerships with other organizations or regulatory bodies to address radioactive waste management challenges in general and cross border cooperation. European projects provide a basis for collaborations regarding the RAW classification system. Except for European projects, also the active participation and follow up of international centres for cooperation (IAEA, NEA/OECD, nucleareurope and World Nuclear Association) in the nuclear field is crucial and applied by European countries.

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Example of a good practice within the country, is UK with the PW IPT facilitates communication and sharing of experience between problematic waste-owning organisations which helps waste owners progress the management of PWs on their sites. The PW IPT is also looking to involve representatives of nuclear new builds and small modular reactors (SMRs), with the aim of helping these industries prevent the generation of problematic wastes in future.

European countries not only give attention to the challenges of RAW classification, definition of problematic waste, inventory of existing “problematic” waste (according to their current definition/understanding of PW), but they also forecast and identify the PW to be generated the future. As e.g. Romania anticipating activated lead and waste contaminated with lead or polonium to be generated by operations of the ALFRED facility at RATEN ICN.

Optimization of RAW management practices is a continuous cyclic process, and enhancement of cross-border cooperation should have a permanent position in the European forum discussions.

3.1.2 Problematic Waste

100% of respondents have a problematic waste in their country, however only respondents from UK and France have an internal (within organization) unified definition for problematic wastes ensuring alignment across departments or stakeholders involved in waste management processes. Therefore, it may be concluded that most of the organizations are waiting for national/international legislation or the world's centres for cooperation in the nuclear field to take over a definition of problematic waste.

The experience of respondents with managing problematic waste within the regulations or guidelines of their country's waste management system, confirm that it is challenging and complex due to: demanding nature in terms of technical level of detail, time and cost; interfaces with stakeholders (WM operators, Regulators, Public, etc.); not available waste management route and related guidelines on problematic waste WAC (only guidelines for WACs for standard waste is available).

European countries are actively addressing the issue of the “problematic waste which is confirmed by the fact that seven out of ten respondents stated that they have plans or experience/solutions applicable for problematic waste in their country. The respondents are searching mainly for the solutions and developing plans for that type of problematic waste, which they have (Question 20) as the problematic waste generated within their country, as it is their responsibility.

The features of waste, which the respondents consider problematic, are included in this report, together with shared internally applied definition of PW (Chapter 3.3). However, any potential common definition of PW shall be examined in terms of robustness (whether it covers the existing and expected “problematic waste” of organizations within Europe).

3.1.3 Waste Classification System in Context of Cross-Border Cooperation

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European countries in terms of waste classification implement the EU directives, or international recommendations for waste classification (e.g. IAEA's Safety Standards Series No. GSG-1/2009; EC council directive 2011/70/EURATOM). Therefore, it is necessary to address and define the “problematic waste” on this international level.

Majority of respondent countries consider the waste classification and waste management system adopted in their country supporting the cross-border cooperation. The main obstacle in terms of cross border cooperation (treatment and conditioning of waste) is therefore not the adopted waste classification and waste management system, but the fact whether the country's legislation allows the RAW export for processing or the import of other countries' RAW for processing and conditioning.

A harmonized radioactive waste classification system across all EC Member States may help to improve cross border cooperation, but it is not a main driver for the improvement of cross-border cooperation. The cross-border cooperation in terms of RAW treatment and conditioning, is a result of international tender with the result based on quality (technologies is the country providing services, extent of minimization of the volume of RAW, etc.) and price (economic efficiency, distance between the countries).

3.1.4 Harmonization (Alignment) of the RAW Classification across EU Member States

Even if majority of EU MS consider the potential harmonization of RAW classification system as beneficial, there are concerns regarding: joint development of the system and, the level of the strictness of the harmonized RAW classification system.

The benefits of harmonized RAW classification system are understood mainly as easier comparison, benchmarking and exchange of information on RAW management practices within Europe. Nevertheless, there are other expected benefits for example, facilitating the use of existing processing facilities across Europe; paving the way toward a harmonized international waste processing and disposal system.

Majority of Respondents' countries has legislation to cover the export/import of radioactive waste to or from other EU Member State; however there is room for improvement.

There are two levels of cooperation (national/ international). On the national level, the cooperation of stakeholders is established mainly due to the clear responsibilities as a result of existing legislation. On international (EU) level providing solid basis for respective countries by following the respective recommendations, the challenge of problematic waste management has a room for extension - of involved parties. Example of good practice is UK having developed a dedicated group for problematic waste management (PW IPT), which may more efficiently represent all stakeholders within UK in supra-national level discussions and projects related to problematic waste.

The main challenges in harmonizing and achieving consistency in waste inventories an achieving consistency in the reporting and management of hazardous waste between individual EU member are: differences in definition of “problematic” vs “hazardous” waste; the

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common definition of the problematic waste should be robust, not omitting any of the specific “problematic” wastes which the countries have or expect to have in the future, issue of sharing of sensitive information, mis-alignment of waste categorisation, issue of acceptance of the common system by respective countries; necessity of demonstration of benefits to stakeholders; necessity of address the specific or general exemption levels, etc.

3.2 Summary of findings from align wastes with treatment technologies in a manner acceptable to all stakeholders

3.2.1 Importance of Waste treatment

The data gathered demonstrates the alignment, and the application of the Waste Hierarchy, noting that there are several criteria which drive decisions (e.g. quantities, shape & dimensions (e.g. large components or small scrap metal) as well as regulatory support and hindrance for treatment of certain waste forms. It was noted that organics (including resins), liquids and metals were the most important for current treatment and that other treatment processes are needed for other waste forms going forward.

3.2.2 Waste Treatments Available - But not used in their MS

This task has highlighted that there are waste treatments available, but are not used. A summary of the reasons for no current treatment being undertaken (with examples) are shown below:

- Waste Acceptance Criteria - Bituminized wastes were noted that they could be treated, but the final disposal Waste Acceptance Criteria (WAC) had not been identified, so no treatment had been undertaken.
- Characterisation - Legacy waste characterisation, moreover the inability to Characterise it, means that these waste forms cannot be sent for treatment and will likely be complicated to qualify for disposal.
- Inability to meet treatment criteria – Liquid organic wastes may need some pretreatment (Separation of solid and liquid) before it can be sent for final treatment. However, some pretreatments can leave a secondary waste that may not have a final treatment process (e.g. liquid waste).
- Historical waste treatment processes are not practical in the current day – Evaporator wastes have previously been dried out, but current waste arisings are small making evaporator treatment ineffective.
- Ability to free release the final product – Current treatment process for insulation material and galvanised material is a difficult and ineffective process, which does not lead to free release, so the processes are not utilised in certain MS.
- Waste treatment option not available in country – Some metals require melting to make recycling efficient, and most MS do not have this capability. The cost of establishing a metal melting facility in each MS is prohibitive. In addition, metals with higher contamination levels may need a limited decay storage upon completion of treatment

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(even though the target always should be immediate release) to avoid disposal of them as radioactive waste, which might neither be allowed in country of treatment nor in country of origin.

- Treatment options are not efficient, or create a larger volume, after treatment – Resins cannot be efficiently treated in certain MS, and that the only main option is grouting. Some can be incinerated in small quantities in certain MS.
- Direct disposal without treatment is possible if the safety case for the repository allows it, however limited in quantities and can be expensive to directly dispose of. Repository safety cases rightly have strict rules and allowances and cannot be adjusted for wastes outside of their parameters. Examples include Bitumen, Asbestos and Organic based wastes. Limited quantities of specific waste forms might be qualified for disposal, but regulators/repository owners try to limit the amounts directly disposed of. There are also examples of when new requirements cause waste already disposed of being retrieved, creating uncertainty of what can be conditioned for disposal which may halt the waste management process and put the waste owners into a wait and see position.
- Transport restrictions or high cost is prohibitive to treatment options when waste is either uncharacterized or of some forms.

3.2.3 Waste Treatments that are acceptable by local stakeholders

Where waste treatments that are available to the waste owners and are used, information has been obtained as to why stakeholders find the treatment process acceptable. A summary of the Stakeholder acceptance views for specific treatments (with examples) are shown below:

- Compliance with the Waste Acceptance Criteria (WAC) – Treatment solution is demonstrated to meet the WAC, which gives sufficient confidence to the regulator and, in applicable cases, the organisation responsible for the disposal of the residuals for disposal at the appropriate facility/repository. An example is with contaminated metals which can be decontaminated and melting where necessary, which allows the demonstration of the WAC post treatment. Please note that some WAC's have not been developed for final disposal facilities and several MS have no disposal sites, making it challenging to develop WACs, as yet.
- Regulator engagement – Dedicated and supported campaigns on specific waste types such as Lead treatment (melting) have been organized with the active engagement of regulators to ensure necessary outcome (NEA-OECD report N°7310 Chapter 4, 2017).
- When the stakeholders support the “Recycling and Reuse” approach (also aligned with the waste hierarchy), it is adopted based on a proven approach with the focus on preserving the environment. Metal treatment (all metal types) is an example of this, and stakeholders support this approach based on the demonstration of its efficiency and understanding of the process. An additional benefit from recycling and reuse of metals is the positive OPEX outcome from the treatment.

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- Stakeholder defines the need to preserve and improve the environment, through the deployment of national policies within MS. Certain treatment processes support this environmental policy aim which in turn facilitate stakeholder support in waste treatment.
- Stakeholders require the waste owners/treatment facilities to demonstrate that the Best Available Techniques (BAT) are adopted and justified to meet the local regulations. Once BAT is adopted, this improves the Stakeholder endorsement of a treatment method. Demonstration for achieving treatment facility emissions during operation is crucial for the wider spread of treatment solutions across MS.
- A longer history of problem-free waste related activities by an organization triggers enhanced support from the local stakeholders, creating work opportunities, tax income, and is regarded as environmentally supportive. This learning is aligned with similar results from polls of the local attitude to nuclear power sites performed in Sweden, where the positive attitude seems to increase the closer you get to the actual site.

3.2.4 Waste Treatments that are NOT acceptable by local stakeholders

Information and opinion gathered has also identified why certain treatments that are not acceptable by stakeholders. A summary of the views raised are shown below:

- Low Technology Readiness Level (TRL) for the treatment process – Additional research and development, or proving works is needed to provide confidence to stakeholders that the proposed treatment process is sufficient, example of this include Beta-Gamma contaminated steels in certain MS. In addition, the disposability of secondary wastes may not have been fully proven. This would mean that the process is not demonstrating Best Available Techniques (BAT).
- Local regulations do not allow for treatment due to the nature of the waste, the treatment process available or the inability to send waste to another country for treatment.
- Individual MS WAC's are not sufficient – Example: Galvanised metals can neither be treated or disposed of in certain countries, even if they have proven metal treatment capabilities, however other MS have the ability to treat galvanised metals and wastes can be sent abroad for treatment.
- Characterization issues prevent treatment – Legacy wastes present a significant challenge for future waste treatment due to the lack of characterization data that can be obtained from the waste.
- Some stakeholders may need more development in the area of waste hierarchy and in particular recycling and reuse of metals – Wastes include Metals and Concrete. The waste hierarchy may not be adopted by the MS.
- Additional pretreatment of wastes (such as repacking) is required before treatment and disposal is required by stakeholders – This applies specifically to R&D and Institutional radioactive originating wastes.

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- Cost of treatment is prohibitive – Stakeholders can allow the treatment of waste forms, but the cost of treatment, or the volume of waste, or the risk profile of the waste, means it's not set as a priority for treatment at this stage (such as highly contaminated steels).

3.2.5 Why wastes are treated or not, and can cross border treatment provide additional options for stakeholders?

The following information provides a summary as to what has been raised as to the reasons for not utilising cross border treatment:

- There are no disposal sites and thus no WACs, making treatment of waste highly uncertain as there are no guarantees that the residue after treatment can be disposed of.
- Local regulations not sufficiently developed - further development needed to see if local regulations can be adopted to send waste to another MS for treatment. Waste facilities can be identified overseas, but local regulations prevent treatment abroad due to some regulatory aspects.
- Waste treatment facilities are not available in certain MS due to low waste volumes making them not economically viable – Such as there is no incinerator or metal treatment in one MS as the waste volume for incineration is too small. This type of waste can be sent abroad for treatment and secondary wastes returned to the originating country.
- Transportation of waste can prove problematic for waste treatment in its own country, in transferring countries, and also for treatment in another MS depending on the Characterization and Activity levels.
- Local waste treatment capability is not sufficient – A specific example of this relates to metal treatment and the potential for sending waste to overseas facilities for treatment due to lack of local capability.
- The cost of treatment and transport is prohibitive – Priority may not be given to certain waste forms.

3.3 Summary of findings from Member States approach to dealing with radioactive contaminated hazardous waste differs

The main conclusions drawn from the information provided by responses to the questionnaire are summarised in this section.

3.3.1 Definition of radioactive hazardous wastes, legislative context and feasibility of cross-border treatment

The task first sought to clarify whether there was a common definition of radioactive hazardous wastes. All MS except for Italy and Denmark reported that hazardous waste definitions are based on EC legislation. Wastes that are both hazardous (in their non-radioactive form) and radioactive are considered in the first instance as radioactive wastes, and are thus subject to

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the relevant radioactive waste regulations. Responses indicated that hazardous waste regulations must also be adhered to, and where these regulations conflict, the most stringent regulations take precedence. Only Italy noted the development of legislation unifying the two separate regulations. The management of radioactive hazardous wastes in other countries might benefit from similar unifying legislation but the situation appears to be manageable. Reasons for the different management options available for radioactive and non-radioactive hazardous wastes were reported as owing to different legislation (or their independent development) and different management concepts and needs.

Regarding the prospect of providing or utilising cross-border treatment options, this appears to be feasible: all MS reported that import/export (to OECD countries) of mercury, asbestos and lead radioactive wastes for treatment is permitted, providing the treated and secondary wastes are returned to the owning nation. EU regulation prohibits the export of hazardous, non-radioactive mercury to non-OECD countries. Only Czechia reported that the import of radioactive waste into its territory is prohibited (although notes an exception for treatment purposes provided the waste is returned to sender). For the radioactive hazardous waste groups that were investigated (mercury, asbestos and lead), the capability to treat and dispose of these wastes is not uniformly available across responding countries, and so the development and utilisation of cross-border solutions could provide a means of overcoming barriers to the management of these wastes.

3.3.1.1 Mercury

Mercury wastes were considered to be hazardous in all responding countries (except Czechia, which appears to be a reflection of the classification as radioactive waste taking precedence). However, significant inventory variation was noted; France, Belgium and the UK reported the highest inventories. Greater volumes of mercury-contaminated wastes compared to radiologically contaminated elemental mercury were common to all respondents where inventory information on both waste types was provided.

No regulations were highlighted as being specific to radioactive mercury wastes, although the UK response did highlight a challenge posed by the implementation of the GWDD for geological disposal, which can be interpreted to preclude the direct discharge of hazardous substances (inc. Hg and Pb) to groundwater for an unspecified time. Further work to explore how this issue is addressed elsewhere would be of benefit to the UK.

The management of mercury wastes can be considered in two parts: the management of radiological elemental mercury, and the management of mercury-contaminated wastes. An established route for the management of radiological elemental mercury was not reported by any MS, although solidification treatments are being investigated by France, Belgium and the UK. Management via incineration of items contaminated with small amounts of mercury was reported by France, Italy and the UK, although this route is strongly affected by the acceptance criteria of the specific incineration plant. In the absence of established management routes, other respondent countries hold their stocks of mercury wastes in storage.

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No common disposal option for radiological mercury waste was reported; only France mentioned that mercury could be disposed of at one of ANDRA's near-surface disposal facilities (Cires and CSA). Regarding the disposal of non-radiological mercury, Lithuania, Italy and France indicated that disposal of stabilised mercury to hazardous landfill is permitted, and the UK highlighted EU legislation that requires stabilised mercury to be disposed of in a salt mine or other deep underground rock formation providing equivalent levels of protection.

3.3.1.2 Asbestos

Asbestos wastes were considered to be hazardous by all respondents (except Czechia, which appears to be a reflection of the classification as radioactive waste taking precedence). There is a high degree of commonality in the sources of radioactive asbestos waste, with the UK reporting the greatest inventory; there are differences in the approach to inventory data reporting that contribute to significant variations in the size of reported inventories.

There was notable variation in the management options reported for radiological forms of asbestos wastes; cementation, thermal treatment, chemical destruction, and sorting and segregation approaches were all mentioned. There also appear to be inconsistent possibilities for VLLW and LLW asbestos disposal, with this being permitted in the UK and France (for which specific WAC apply) but prohibited in Czechia. Similar variations in approaches to non-radioactive asbestos management were observed.

3.3.1.3 Lead

Most respondents considered lead waste to be hazardous, although some exceptions were made, e.g. for bulk metallic lead in Italy. The response for Czechia, classifying lead as a radioactive rather than hazardous waste, appears to be a reflection of the classification as radioactive waste taking precedence. The sources, quantities and chemical/physical forms of radioactive lead wastes varied considerably from country to country, and future construction of SMR/AMRs utilising lead as a coolant was noted as a potential future source. Please note that radioactive lead can be decontaminated, cleared and released to the conventional metal industry as a common practice in certain established metal treatment facilities.

Whilst approaches to management appeared to be at different stages of development amongst MS, it was common for respondent countries to possess the capability to condition or decontaminate radiological lead wastes. Around half the MS represented (France, Belgium Romania and the UK) had NSD routes available for radiological lead disposal, although France noted the challenges in continuing to utilise this route if forecast inventories increase significantly.

Recycling and reuse of non-radiological lead was common to all MS; however, this was only mentioned in the context of radiological lead wastes by Belgium and Sweden. Well-established disposal routes for non-radiological lead wastes were also commonly reported. However, metallic lead to be recycled to the extent reasonable.

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3.4 Potential benefits and impacts

Throughout the HARPERS project, the needs, challenges and benefits of Cross Border Waste Management have been identified and refined. The relevant aspects of these benefits have been used in the Cases for Change highlighted in the WP3 Business Case Milestone and are summarised below.

1. Optimized Use of Existing Infrastructure

Cross-border nuclear waste treatment enables member states to leverage advanced facilities and technologies available in other countries. This reduces the need for individual nations to invest in costly infrastructure, particularly those with limited nuclear programs or smaller quantities of waste. Using joint BAT facilities also support a sustainable society. Countries like France, Sweden, and Finland, which possess some state-of-the-art waste treatment and storage facilities, can provide services to neighbouring states, maximizing the efficiency and utility of these resources.

2. Enhanced Safety Standards

By consolidating nuclear waste treatment in facilities with proven safety records, cross-border cooperation can enhance overall safety. Advanced facilities are often equipped with cutting-edge technologies and staffed by highly trained personnel, reducing the risks associated with waste handling and storage. This collective approach can improve safety outcomes across the region.

3. Cost Efficiency

Treating nuclear waste across borders can lead to significant cost savings for member states. Developing and maintaining national facilities for all types of nuclear waste is financially burdensome, particularly for countries with limited nuclear energy programs. Sharing resources and facilities allows for economies of scale, reducing the per-unit cost of waste treatment and storage.

4. Accelerated Progress on Long-Term Solutions

Cross-border collaboration can expedite the development and implementation of long-term nuclear waste management solutions, such as deep geological repositories. By pooling financial and technical resources, member states can advance projects more efficiently, reducing delays and ensuring timely progress toward permanent disposal solutions.

5. Strengthened European Solidarity and Cooperation

Cooperating on nuclear waste treatment fosters a sense of solidarity and shared responsibility among EU member states. This collaborative approach aligns with the EU's broader goals of promoting unity and mutual support. It also helps to build trust and strengthen political and technical relationships between countries.

6. Improved Environmental Protection

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Consolidating nuclear waste treatment in well-regulated, advanced facilities minimizes the environmental risks associated with improper waste handling and storage. Centralized treatment and disposal ensure that waste is managed in a manner that adheres to the highest environmental standards, reducing the potential for contamination and long-term ecological harm.

7. Knowledge Sharing and Capacity Building

Cross-border waste treatment facilitates the exchange of technical expertise and best practices between member states. Countries with less experience in nuclear waste management can benefit from the knowledge and skills of their more advanced counterparts. This not only enhances the capabilities of individual nations but also strengthens the EU's overall capacity to manage nuclear waste safely and effectively.

In summary, the cross-border treatment of nuclear waste offers numerous benefits for European member states, ranging from cost efficiency and enhanced safety to environmental protection and strengthened regional cooperation. By working together, EU countries can ensure the safe, sustainable, and effective management of radioactive materials, supporting the region's energy and environmental goals while fostering a spirit of unity and collaboration.

4 Conclusion and Recommendations

The cross-border treatment of nuclear waste in European member states is a multifaceted challenge that requires careful coordination and collaboration. Addressing regulatory disparities, mitigating transportation risks, managing public perception, and resolving questions of equity are essential steps toward effective cross-border waste management. By fostering trust, enhancing infrastructure, and promoting transparency, the EU can strengthen its collective approach to nuclear waste treatment while ensuring safety and sustainability for future generations.

Cross border radioactive waste management can result in significant benefits including:

- Reducing the cost of treatment,
- Encouragement of smaller waste inventories to be treated
- Utilising the availability of technology
- Benefiting from variances in national regulatory policy/priorities.

More generally, cross border treatment can support the circular economy principles for certain wastes/assets but can also contribute to a more sustainable and resource-efficient approach to nuclear decommissioning and radioactive waste management.

Across the three topics explored in detail in this WP, there are a series of recommendations that are summarized below which will help to continue the alignment to the waste hierarchy for MS.

From a **Regulatory** perspective the recommendations are:

- Ensure that each MS's legislation allows the radioactive waste export for processing or the import of other countries' radioactive waste for processing and conditioning, mirrored with legislation for retrieval of secondary waste after treatment.
- Resolution of the regulatory conflicts at a National and European level regarding waste which is both radioactive and hazardous.
- Some MS are not part of OECD, so cannot benefit from utilising cross-border treatment options, this must be resolved to promote waste management best practice.

From a **Technical** point of view:

- Some MS do not have sufficient infrastructure to handle waste, leading to delays or inaction. The recommendation is that a European platform is developed to identify all European infrastructure available for use by MS.
- Compliance with the Waste Acceptance Criteria (WAC) must be declared to the Regulator for disposal at the appropriate facility/repository. WAC have not been developed for some types of waste's final disposal.
- Ensure that waste management techniques are sufficiently demonstrated for national regulators or waste owners – this must cover simple and complex waste forms and

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ensure that there is a suitable forum for sharing information across MS for MS stakeholders to engage with and develop the necessary requirements to allow for internal treatment, or utilising cross border facilities

- Ensure that a Europe (All MS's) agree the definition of problematic waste and that it is included within the individual MS legislation. European countries in terms of waste classification implement the EU directives, or international recommendations for waste classification (e.g. IAEA's Safety Standards Series No. GSG-1/2009; EC council directive 2011/70/EURATOM). Therefore, it is necessary to address and define the "problematic waste" on this supra-national level.
- Consistency in inventory information, naming, reporting and management is required for problematic was and also for hazardous waste which is also radioactive. Therefore, there needs to be a common definition of the problematic waste which is robust, and does not omit any of the specific "problematic" wastes which the MS have. This will then allow the successful sharing of information, removal of the misalignment of waste categorisation, and allow for a common acceptance system by respective MS which will lead to cross border waste management.
- More examples of good practice are needed to be communicated – for example: Example of a good practice regarding the activities of a regulator within the country is UK with the PW IPT (a Nuclear Decommissioning Authority-funded group), which facilitates communication and sharing of experience between problematic waste-owning organisations which helps waste owners progress the management or PWs on their sites. The PW IPT is also looking to involve representatives of nuclear new builds and small modular reactors (SMRs), with the aim of helping these industries prevent the generation of problematic wastes in future.
- The majority of EU countries do not have the definition of problematic waste included within their legislation. European countries in terms of waste classification implement the EU directives, or international recommendations for waste classification (e.g. IAEA's Safety Standards Series No. GSG-1/2009; EC council directive 2011/70/EURATOM). Therefore, it is necessary to address and define the "problematic waste" on this supra-national level.
- Define European wide Best Available Technology (BAT) approach for material and waste characterisation and treatment, based on established practices and new approaches. European wide agreed approaches may incentivise cross border facilities and services.
- For the radioactive hazardous waste groups that were investigated (mercury, asbestos and lead), the capability to treat and dispose of these wastes was not uniformly available across responding countries, so the development and utilisation of cross-border solutions could provide a means of overcoming current barriers to the management of these wastes. This is particularly relevant where countries have small inventories, for which it could be disproportionately costly to develop dedicated national treatment facilities. Treatment and onward management of elemental mercury appears

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to be a promising candidate for future collaborative effort to establish shared or harmonised best practice strategies.

- There appears to be a strong case for enhanced recycling / reuse of radiologically contaminated lead wastes, noting that there is expected to be future demand for this material, e.g. as a coolant in some SMR/AMR designs. Recycling radiological lead is current practice in a small number of countries, but disposal routes are more commonly reported. Therefore, it is recommended to examine the feasibility of applying existing decontamination capabilities more widely (and/or expanding these capabilities).
- Reduce the stocks of legacy/historical radioactive waste in Europe by co-founded shared treatment facilities across borders.
- Generate a set of standard Waste Acceptance Criteria (WAC), standardised packages etc. for new disposal facilities in Europe which may also incentivise cross border facilities and services.
- Secure that investments in facilities and arrangements for shared cross border facilities and services should, as outlined in the Analysis Section, in a well-defined way address
 - technical needs by the nuclear industry waste owners interested in taking benefit cross border treatment
 - regulatory requirements of the involved authorities
 - environmental protection and sustainability aspects
 - commercial and operational aspects related to the cross-border facilities including facility utilisation, economy of scale, full life cycle cost and financial risks
 - political and sociopolitical expectations including reduction of the stock of untreated radioactive waste, shorter decommissioning projects, safe transports and handling and loss of local jobs
- Alignment of MS priorities for managing nuclear waste based on political, environmental, or public concerns through:
 - Setting clear policies leading to establishing sufficient infrastructure to handle waste.
 - Developing WAC which are aligned across MS, but that are also appropriate for local regulators/facilities for all waste forms.
 - Establish dedicated regulator engagement events covering the alignment of the wastes with treatment technologies, to ensure that it is well understood also by the intergovernmental agencies and forums. Dedicated and supported campaigns on specific waste types such as Lead treatment (melting) have been organized with the active engagement of regulators to ensure necessary outcome (NEA/OECD report N°7310 Chapter 4, 2017).
 - Demonstration for achieving treatment facility emissions during operation also to the regulators and stakeholders of other MS may support the wider spread of treatment solutions across MS.

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- The main obstacle in terms of cross border cooperation (treatment and conditioning of waste) is the country's legislation (noting that different MS have different structure, format, terminology and requirements to their legislations) which can allow the RAW export for processing or the import of other countries' RAW for processing and conditioning. However, it is recommended that there is enhancement of lines of communication for cross-border cooperation.

By adopting these recommendations and fostering a collaborative approach among stakeholders, the nuclear industry can improve the way it manages its radioactive waste through the utilisation of cross border facilities.

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